

Чоршанбиев Умар Равшан угли

Chorshanbiev Umar Ravshan ugli

Докторант

doctoral student

Ибадуллаев Ахмаджон

Ibadullaev Ahmadjon

Профессор

Professor

Бабаев Аскар Рузибадалович

Babaev Askar Ruzibadalovich

Доцент

Associate professor

Ташкентский государственный

транспортный университет

Ташкент, Узбекистан

Tashkent State transport University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ВЛИЯНИЕ УМЕНЬШЕНИЯ СЦЕПЛЕНИЯ ВОДНО-ДИСПЕРСИОННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ НА РАБОЧИЕ УСТРОЙСТВА В ГИДРОТРАНСПОРТНЫХ СИСТЕМАХ

THE EFFECT OF WATER DISPERSION SYSTEM COUPLING REDUCTION ON WORKING DEVICES IN HYDROTRANSPORT SYSTEMS

Аннотация. На горнодобывающих, металлургических, химических, машиностроительных и строительных предприятиях гидравлические транспортные системы используются для обеспечения переноса водно-дисперсионных систем из одного места в другое. В статье анализируется влияние вязкости дисперсных систем на рабочие устройства в гидротранспортных системах, гидродинамика потока, основные

закономерности сопротивления рабочих устройств гидравлическому сопротивлению.

Abstract. In mining, metallurgical, chemical, machine-building and construction enterprises, hydraulic transport systems are used to ensure the transfer of aqueous dispersion systems from one place to another. The article analyzes the effect of the viscosity of dispersed systems on the working devices in hydraulic transport systems, flow hydrodynamics, the basic laws of the resistance of working devices to hydraulic resistance.

Ключевые слова: дисперсионная система, модификация, вязкость, гидравлический транспорт, гидравлические потери, насос, двигатель, труба.

Keywords: Dispersion system, modification, viscosity, hydraulic transport, hydraulic loss, pump, engine, pipe.

Introduction. In the process of using hydraulic transport systems, the speed of flow, the operating condition of the working devices and their operating time depend on the structural and mechanical properties of the dispersed systems. In the study of the state of dispersed systems, the viscosity has a special place. Therefore, the viscosity analysis of dispersed systems is required [1].

Main part. The viscosity phenomenon occurs when liquids move and resists the movement of dispersed systems in liquids. The higher the viscosity, the greater the force expended to overcome this resistance. The degree of viscosity is determined by a quantity called the viscosity coefficient [2].

In accordance with I. Newton's law, the voltage generated under the influence of external force is proportional to the degree of the velocity of the silencer, which is spent to overcome the viscosity between the fluid layers::

$$\tau = \eta * \gamma \quad \text{or} \quad \tau = \eta \frac{du}{dx} \quad (1)$$

where $\eta = \tau/\gamma$ is the viscosity of the fluid (or internal friction).

The viscosity of substances differs sharply from one another. For example, the viscosity of water at 20 °C is equal to 10^{-2} пуаз ($\frac{\text{r}}{\text{cm.c}} \text{ ra}$) or 10^{-3} Pa * s. The viscosity of solids can be as large as 10^{15} - 10^{20} Pa * s [3].

If the dispersed phase particles are loosely connected to each other, the mechanical properties of the dispersion medium the dispersed phase varies less than the presence. Therefore, dispersed systems are: 1) structured and unstructured systems are divided into two. Unstructured systems include conventional dilute sols, suspensions, and emulsions. These systems do not have mechanical strength. But their viscosity is slightly higher than the viscosity of a pure dispersion medium: It can be found calculated on the basis of the equation Einsteineyn.

$$\eta = \eta_0 * (1 + k\varphi) \quad (2)$$

where: φ - volumetric concentration of the dispersion phase, $\varphi \frac{v}{v_0}$ such: v – the size of the dispersed phase particle, v_0 - dispersion medium size, η_0 - viscosity of the environment, k – coefficient, which depends on the particle shape. It is known from the equation (2) that the viscosity of the dispersion system is proportional to the concentration of the dispersion phase [3].

The reason why the viscosity of disperse systems is higher than the viscosity of the dispersion medium is that in such systems, the dispersed phase particles interfere with the flow of fluid. Therefore, as the dispersed phase concentration increases, the viscosity of the dispersed system increases. In 1906, Einstein, based on hydrodynamic considerations and assuming that the molecules of the solute were spherical in structure, found a relationship (formula 2) between the viscosity (η) of the solution and the viscosity of the pure solvent (η_0).

Usually the viscosity of normal liquids does not depend on the pressure, that is, even when the pressure increases, the viscosity remains unchanged. Some dispersive system (aluminum, gold, platinum, copper, etc.k. ores) liquids are subject to the law of Puazel at small pressures and are in laminar motion:

$$\eta = \frac{\pi * \rho * r^2 * t}{8vl} \quad (3)$$

Where l – is the length of the capillary, r – its radius, t – is the time, $\pi=3,14$, v – is the volume of the liquid flowing through the capillary t in time, p – is the pressure. When the pressure is increased, the laminar action becomes a turbulent action. According to the law of Puazel, the multiplication of pressure by Time $P \cdot t$ must be an invariable value [2].

The viscosity of disperse systems that changes with pressure change is called their structural viscosity. The reason for the origin of the structure viscosity is that the internal structures formed in the solution make it difficult for the fluid to flow. Disperse phase particles block the path of the liquid layers and slow down this movement, if the particles of a longer shape cross the flow of the liquid, they greatly impede the movement of the liquid [4].

The slowdown of the flow has a negative impact on the performance of working devices in hydraulic systems. In the flow of dispersed systems moving in pipes, energy loss due to the viscosity force occurs H_{1-2} , the energy consumption is used to overcome the viscosity force. When we examine the flow motion of dispersed systems in pipes, the problem mainly comes to the calculation of the loss expended to overcome the frictional force. It takes the following approach to hydraulic loss:

$$H_{1-2} = \frac{\tau \pi D l}{\gamma S} \quad (4)$$

Where: τ – stress is the force of tension or comparable friction, that is, the force of friction that corresponds to the surface of the unit; l – flow length; D – pipe diameter; $\chi = \pi D$ – hinged perimeter.

The hydraulic loss depends on the kinetic energy of the fluid, which increases with increasing energy and decreases with decreasing energy. The hydraulic loss is therefore obtained in proportion to the kinetic energy of the fluid.

The viscosity of dispersed systems affects the flow process in the pump, which is known in the efficiency of the pump. When transmitting disperse system fluids, the power expended by the pump motors to rotate the shaft will be much greater than the amount calculated by these formulas. The difference in useful power from the power

supplied by the motor to the shaft is spent on overcoming various resistances in lifting the fluid.

It is said that the useful working coefficient (UWC) of the pump is the ratio of the useful capacity to the given capacity given to the Val:

$$\eta = \frac{N_u}{N} \quad (5)$$

UWC η FIC is the expression of all energy losses in the liquid. These losses fall into three categories: hydraulic, mechanical, and volumetric.

Hydraulic losses – The hydraulic resistances in the pump are involved in the inlet and outlet of the pump, in the formation of pumps, etc. is the energy used to overcome hydraulic friction in. These losses are taken into account by the hydraulic UWC:

$$\eta_h = \frac{H}{H + \sum h_{wpump}} \quad (6)$$

where $\sum h_{wpump}$ – the sum of the losses in the pump. Hydraulic UWC depends on the working parts of the pump and the quality of preparation of the pump in general.

Mechanical losses – the friction in the pump bearings, the crankshaft - the power losses spent on the connecting rods and their own needs, which are taken into account by the mechanical UWC.

$$\eta_m = \frac{N_i}{N_b} \quad (7)$$

where N_i – is the indicator power of the pump, equal to the difference between the power of the pump shaft and the power dissipated for mechanical losses. ($N_i = N_b - N_u$). Mechanical UWC - characterizes the quality of workmanship and fit of bearings, bearings and other friction parts.

Volume losses – it occurs as a result of fluid leakage through the turbines, valves in the pump and insufficient filling of the working chambers of the pump. Volumetric UWC η_v is represented as follows:

$$\eta_v = \frac{Q}{Q + \Delta Q} \quad (8)$$

where ΔQ – volumetric losses of fluid in the pump. The volumetric UWC characterizes the level of germeticity and operating conditions of the pump [2].

Research results. In reducing the effect of the viscosity of dispersed systems on the working devices in hydraulic systems, it is possible to increase or decrease the formation of structures by changing the properties of the system by adding surface modifiers (surfactants or electrolytes) to the system. When an electrolyte is added to an aqueous disperse system, the surface of the particles is dehydrated and the structure is enhanced, resulting in a decrease in viscosity. The decrease in viscosity increases the UWC of the working devices.

Conclusion

In calculating the effect of the viscosity of dispersed systems on working devices in hydraulic systems, it was found that the working devices consume large amounts of energy to overcome the viscosity. The direct impact of the energy expended on the UWC has been mentioned above. Internal corrosion of pipes occurs as a result of the movement of the flow of disperse systems in the pipes being resisted due to viscosity. Slowing down the flow movement affects time productivity and leads to excessive energy consumption. Excessive energy consumption and loss of time efficiency in transmitting the flow of dispersed systems through the pumps leads to wear of the working devices, which affects the service life. This represents the urgency of the problem. Reducing viscosity and maintaining FIC serve to achieve cost-effectiveness.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhimov, K., Babaev, A., Chorshanbiev, U., & Obidjonov, A. (2021). Modification of dispersion systems and its motion in cylindrical pipes. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 264). EDP Sciences. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202126403026>
2. Қ. Латипов, С.Эргашев. Гидравлика и гидромашины. Учебное пособие.Т: 1986, С. 57-68.

3. К. С. Ахмедов, Ҳ.Р. Раҳимов. Коллоидная химия. учебное пособие. Т: 1993, С. 123-127.
4. Makhkamov D. A., Chorshanbiev U. R., Babaev A. R. Laboratory Research of Multiple Flow Movement in Pipelines //Global Scientific Review. – 2022. – Т. 1. – С. 42-46.